

Australian Research Data Commons

Researcher Case Studies

TEMPLATE

Skilled Workforce Development Team, ARDC

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What is this template for?

This template shows how a service, tool, dataset, or framework has been used in your research. It helps other researchers understand its impact and provides tips to make it easier for them to use. These case studies are published in the Resources section of the ARDC website.

How to use this template

1. Replace the italicised prompt text with your own words.
2. Keep it as simple as possible, avoid technical jargon if possible.
3. Modify the template to suit your context.
4. Pages 3 -11 are worked examples
5. Test your case study! Consider obtaining feedback from those who are unfamiliar with the topic.

Add your topic here Case Study

Case study author(s):

Add author name, affiliation

Add author name, affiliation

FEATURED SERVICE/TOOL/DATASET/ FRAMEWORK	IMAGE
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • What is the service/tool/dataset/ framework that is being featured? • How does it help researchers? <p>[Add a video clip of presentation, if available]</p> <p><i>[insert name of project]</i> received investment (<i>insert project DOI</i>) from the Australian Research Data Commons (ARDC). The ARDC is enabled by the National Collaborative Research Infrastructure Strategy (NCRIS).</p>	<p>Add image(s) that helps researchers understand how the featured service/tool/dataset/ framework supports research.</p> <p>Describe what the image(s) show.</p>
LEARNING TAKEAWAYS	AUDIENCE
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • How does the case study help researchers understand the featured service/tool/dataset/ framework? 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Who should use this?
RELATED OUTPUTS	
<p><i>Add published papers and outputs which relate to this topic here.</i></p>	
CONTEXT - PROJECT OVERVIEW	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • What was the research question? • What did it aim to achieve? • Who was doing the research? 	
HOW THE SERVICE/TOOL/DATASET/Framework WAS USED	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • What was the research workflow? • How was the service/tool/dataset/ framework used? • Were all the features used? 	

IMPACT OF USING SERVICE/TOOL/DATASET/Framework	USER TIPS
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • What features made it a better choice than alternatives? • Did it save time, provide new insights, improve discoverability? 	<p>Include false starts, workarounds, surprises - anything that you wish you knew before you used it in research.</p>
FURTHER INFORMATION	
<p>About the project Learn more about the project at <i>[add links to the project page here]</i> Watch a short video about the project at <i>[add link to video clip here]</i></p>	<p>Recommended further reading <i>[Add links to relevant learning resources here]</i></p>

EXAMPLE ONLY

(Read the [published case study](#))

Time Layered Cultural Maps (TLC Map) case studies:

1. Tracking early Pacific scientific voyages

2. Locating Australian monuments

Case study author(s):

Dr Claire Brennan, James Cook University (JCU)

Dr Ana Stevenson, Anglicare Southern Queensland and University of Southern Queensland

Case study 1: Coral Discovery Project

FEATURED SERVICE/TOOL/DATASET/ FRAMEWORK

- *What is the service/tool/dataset/ framework that is being featured?*
- *How does it help researchers?*

What is TLC Map ?

[TLC Map](#) is a free online tool to create digital maps for humanities social science research.

TLC Map helps researchers collate historical information from many different sources into a single visual display, making comparative insight far easier.

Researchers can upload a data set of geographic coordinates, dates/times and event descriptions, and TLC Maps uses that to create an interactive map.

Users can control the map view to see what happened at the same time or at the same location.

IMAGE

Add image(s) that helps researchers understand how the featured service/tool/dataset/ framework supports research.

Describe what the image(s) show.

Image of voyage paths at [Coral Discovery project on TLC Map](#)

<p>The 2 case studies below show the TLC Map being used to collate and display:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. European scientific expedition voyages in the Pacific before 1834 2. Monuments and “Big Things” across Australia. <p>The case studies were presented on 5 February 2025 at the 2025 ARDC HASS and Indigenous Research Data Commons Summer School by Dr Claire Brennan, James Cook University (JCU) and Dr Ana Stevenson, Anglicare Southern Queensland and University of Southern Queensland.</p> <p>[Add a video clip of presentation, if available]</p> <p>In this case study, you can watch the recording of the presentation, and/or read the key takeaways below.</p> <p>HASS & Indigenous Summer School 2025 - Case Study: Use of the Time Layered Cultural Maps</p> <p>[Acknowledge the ARDC - Download our acknowledgment kit from our website]</p> <p>ARDC has supported TLCmap through co-investment (https://doi.org/10.47486/PL069 and https://doi.org/10.47486/HIR007) and TLCmap is hosted on the ARDC Nectar Research Cloud.</p>	
<p>LEARNING TAKEAWAYS</p>	<p>AUDIENCE</p>
<p><i>How does the case study help researchers understand the featured service/tool/dataset/ framework?</i></p> <p>This case study helps you</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Understand what TLC Map does ● See how TLC Map is used in place-based research ● Learn tips for using TLC Map. 	<p><i>Who should use this?</i></p> <p>This case study is for humanities researchers, particularly those researching history, as well as those conducting interdisciplinary research.</p> <p>The TLCMaps featured in this case study are an open-access resource that can be used by history and social studies teachers at all levels, from primary and secondary school through to tertiary education.</p>

RELATED OUTPUTS

Add published papers and outputs which relate to this topic here.

View the recording and slides for this case study as presented at the 2025 ARDC HASS and Indigenous Research Data Commons Summer School:

[recording](#)
[slides](#) [pptx].

Also read the following:

- Claire Brennan, “Land and Sea: The Significance of Named Places in Digitally Mapping Historic Ocean Voyages,” *M/C Journal* 27, no. 5 (2024).
- Claire Brennan and Ana Stevenson, “Monumentally Kitsch: The Decommissioned Captain Cook Statues of Aotearoa (New Zealand) and Australia,” *Radical History Review* 152, Special Edition: “Memory Over Forgetting: Monuments, Memorials and Intangible Heritage,” eds. Bonita Bennett, Bonny Ibhawoh, Alex Lichtenstein, and Daniel Walkowitz (2025): 32-52.
- the [Expeditions to the Pacific](#) website
- the [Colonial Commemorative Landscapes in Australia](#) website.

CONTEXT - PROJECT OVERVIEW

- *What was the research question?*
- *What did it aim to achieve?*
- *Who was doing the research?*

About the project

The Coral Discovery project is digitally mapping all European scientific expeditions that left records of journeys in the Indian and Pacific Oceans before 1834. The project arose from a meeting between an environmental historian, a shipwreck archaeologist and a coral taxonomist, and now involves anthropologists and environmental scientists. By linking historical places and times to the physical samples collected during those scientific voyages, the project will help scientists gain deeper insights on the past state of the environment.

The project is a partnership between James Cook University and the Queensland Museum network. The project members are: Dr Claire Brennan and Dr Alana Grech, JCU; Adjunct Professor Andrew Baird, JCU; Dr Tom Bridge, JCU and Queensland Museum; Maddy McAllister, JCU and Queensland Museum; and Professor Koen Stapelbroek, JCU.

HOW THE SERVICE/TOOL/DATASET/Framework WAS USED

- *What was the research workflow?*
- *How was the service/tool/dataset/framework used?*
- *Were all the features used?*

How the TLC Map was used

The first step in the project, “Expeditions to the Pacific”, involves mapping and then analysing European scientific expeditions that left Europe for the Pacific between 1768 and 1834.

Data for TLC Map is drawn from the diaries and maps of explorers and seafarers. Around 70 datasets have been created from publicly available diaries and journals, for example the [1766 Bougainville expedition](#) sourced from the [Internet Archive copy of a Voyage Round the World by The King's Frigate La Boudeuse and the Supply Ship L'Etoile](#) by Louis Antoine de Bougainville (translated by John Fegan).

The research project involves 3 elements:

1. The datasets stored in the [research data repository at James Cook University](#)
2. The [Coral Discovery Maps at the TLC Map site](#), which draws on this data to create the interactive visualisation
3. The [Expeditions to the Pacific website](#), using WordPress, where users can search between datasets for many different voyages directly and view these individually using the TLC Map.

The layers feature of TLC Maps allowed the researchers to create a [different layer for each voyage](#). They could view and process data from one voyage without this impacting the other layers.

Several types of views are possible with TLC Maps, for example all data points relevant to a particular year, displayed across a map. This project uses a view that displays locations visited by a single voyage, with lines connecting the first location visited with the second, and so on, to show the expedition path.

Mapping the journeys using the TLC Map allows researchers to easily compare these. Researchers can focus on either the routes of particular ships or on particular places. They can see which expeditions visited the same place across time.

IMPACT OF USING SERVICE/TOOL/DATASET/Framework	USER TIPS
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>What features made it a better choice than alternatives?</i> • <i>Did it save time, provide new insights, improve discoverability?</i> <p>The impact of using TLC Map</p> <p><i>TLC Map underpins the Expeditions to the Pacific. This allows both scientists and humanities researchers to understand this collection of voyages at any scale in their interrogations of the past. Users can trace the distribution of collections</i></p>	<p><i>Include false starts, workarounds, surprises - anything that you wish you knew before you used it in research.</i></p> <p>User tips added at the end of the 2 case studies.</p>

central to European science’s understanding of the world and identify scientific collection sites.

In the future, the data collected through the Expeditions to the Pacific project may be used to locate relevant sites for coral topotype DNA collection. In addition, information from the journals could be used to establish environmental baselines for the places visited, and could be used to track environmental change over time. The project may also help in identifying the origins of museum collections, which could be significant for repatriation.

FURTHER INFORMATION

Learn more about the [project and view the TLC Maps](#).

Watch a short video about the project from JCU

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=5NYt7D-xVJo>

Further reading details added at the end of the 2 case studies.

Case study 2: Mapping Monuments

FEATURED SERVICE/TOOL/DATASET/ FRAMEWORK

- What is the service/tool/dataset/ framework that is being featured?
- How does it help researchers?

Not applicable - these details have been outlined in Case Study 1.

Add image(s) that helps researchers understand how the featured service/tool/dataset/ framework supports research.

Describe what the image(s) show.

Image showing [Mapping Monuments Figurative Statues TLC Map](#) with time-slider set to different years

CONTEXT - PROJECT OVERVIEW

- What was the research question?
- What did it aim to achieve?
- Who was doing the research?

About the project

[Mapping Monuments](#) uses the TLC Map to create a timeline map of Australian monuments, with particular attention to colonial commemorations and figurative statues. “Big Things” form a sub-collection, searchable separately. “Big Things” were included as significant monuments across the landscape. Although there is no established criteria to identify what is a monument versus what is a Big Thing, the recent work of architectural historian Amy Clarke is particularly important in defining the latter.

This project brings together historians from the University of Southern Queensland and James Cook University. The project members are Dr Claire Brennan (JCU), Dr Ana Stevenson (Anglicare Southern Queensland and USQ), and Kaitlin Mills (USQ). The data collection for this TLC Map was funded through a 2024 Centre for Heritage and Culture Small Research Grant.

HOW THE SERVICE/TOOL/DATASET/Framework WAS USED

- What was the research workflow?
- How was the service/tool/dataset/ framework used?
- Were all the features used?

How the TLC Map was used

Data was initially sourced from [Monument Australia](#) and supplemented by “Big Things” data, initially drawn from Wikipedia.

Like the Coral Discovery maps, the data itself is stored separately from the TLC Map interface. The [Mapping Monuments research project site allows the user to navigate between the different TLC Map views and provides more information about each dataset](#)

IMPACT OF USING SERVICE/TOOL/DATASET/Framework	USER TIPS
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>What features made it a better choice than alternatives?</i> • <i>Did it save time, provide new insights, improve discoverability?</i> <p>The Impact of Using TLC Map</p> <p>The metadata in each monument record allows users to quickly see on the TLC Map the location of all monuments matching a criterion like “human figure”. This enables critique of Australia’s monuments through analysis of their representation of gender, colonial history, race, and other elements. This way of interrogating the data made it clear to the research team that traditional statues tend to be metropolitan, while Big Things tend to be regional. The temporal element of TLC Map makes it possible to see when commemoration of various types of events and persons was undertaken, facilitating recognition of what types of heritage have been important at different times.</p>	<p><i>Include false starts, workarounds, surprises - anything that you wish you knew before you used it in research.</i></p> <p>Tips for using TLC Map</p> <p>Dr Brennan and Dr Stevenson shared their insights on using TLC Map in research projects.</p> <p>Tips about wrangling data to use with TLC Maps</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Using “Big Things” data from Wikipedia was not simple. It often was not easy to obtain latitude and longitude. • The negative character in latitude coordinates is significant. Initially several Australian “Big Things” displayed in Japan and Europe before the lack of the negative sign was noticed. • It is important to develop criteria for how to represent uncertain dates because TLC Map requires exact dates. Often a starting date was not available for monuments, so the researchers’ approach involved estimating and adding a nominal date instead. <p>Tips about using the TLC Map interface:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The TLC may not have fields to match each bit of metadata in the original dataset, and has character limits on what can be seen when the user clicks on a location pin. The Big Things project added: latitude, longitude, place, name, description, start date, end date, and a single link back to a reference. Fuller data can be easily provided via links to external datasets.

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● TLC Maps is very much a backend. It's not a shopfront. If you're embarking on a TLC project, you do need to consider what your shopfront is going to be, for example the Expeditions to the Pacific site in this case. ● There are some frustrations with dealing with TLC Map. You need some patience. And if you make a mistake on a map, often you are better to trash the entire map and start again. ● It's best to refine and improve the data on the local source, rather than trying to do this directly in the TLC Map interface. ● Other digital tools, including Google My Maps and Streetview, can be useful for small tasks with simple data. ● Using a multi-layer map, even if you have only one layer, will provide more stability as it creates a permanent URL even if the underlying map is trashed and recreated <p>Overall, Dr Brennan and Dr Stevenson emphasised that although digital projects may appear easy on the surface, they take a long time to produce.</p>
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FURTHER INFORMATION

<p>Not applicable - Links to the project page and to the video clip of the project have been outlined in Case Study 1.</p>	<p><i>[Add links to relevant learning resources here]</i></p> <p>Recommended Further Reading Arthur, Paul Longley, Erik Champion, Hugh Craig, Ning Gu, Mark Harvey, Victoria Haskins, Andrew May, Bill Pascoe, Alana Piper, Lyndall Ryan, Rosalind Smith, and Deb Verhoeven, "Time-Layered Cultural Map of Australia," <i>Proceedings of the Digital Humanities in the Nordic Countries 5th Conference</i>, eds. Sanita Reinsone, Inguna Skadiņa, Anda Baklāne, and Jānis Daugavietis (Central Europe Workshop Proceedings, 2020), 184-191.</p> <p>Brennan, Claire, "Digital Humanities, Digital Methods, Digital History, and Digital Outputs: History Writing and the Digital Revolution," <i>History Compass</i> 16, no. 10 (2018): 1-12.</p>
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	<p>Brennan, Claire, "Land and Sea: The Significance of Named Places in Digitally Mapping Historic Ocean Voyages," <i>M/C Journal</i> 27, no. 5 (2024).</p> <p>Brennan, Claire and Ana Stevenson, "Monumentally Kitsch: The Decommissioned Captain Cook Statues of Aotearoa (New Zealand) and Australia," <i>Radical History Review</i>, Special Edition: "Memory Over Forgetting: Monuments, Memorials and Intangible Heritage," eds. Bonita Bennett, Bonny Ibhawoh, Alex Lichtenstein, and Daniel Walkowitz (2025): 32-52.</p> <p>Clarke, Amy, "Making a Mark: Displays of Regional and National Identity in the Big Things of Australia and Canada," <i>Journal of Australian Studies</i> 47, no. 2 (2023): 238-55.</p> <p>Clarke, Amy, "The Commercial and Regional Imagery of Big Things: Establishing a Foundation for the Study of Oversized Roadside Landmarks," <i>Journal of Material Culture</i> 29, no. 1 (2024): 3-25.</p> <p>Jones, Mike, and Alana Piper, "Digital History," <i>Australian Historical Studies</i> 55, no. 1 (2024): 178-203.</p> <p>Nichols, Julie, Uncle Lindsay Thomas, Travis Thomas, Jared Thomas, Fu Hong Tang, and Delene Weber, "Terrains of Country: Mapping Co-Design Methods," <i>ASEAN Journal of Community Engagement</i> 8, no. 2 (2024): 142-163.</p> <p>Piper, Alana, "What Is Digital History?" <i>Public History Review</i> 28 (2021): 1-4.</p> <p>Ryan, Lyndall, "Newspaper Evidence of Colonial Frontier Massacres in Australia," <i>History Australia</i> 18, no. 4 (2021): 845-849.</p> <p>Ryan, Lyndall, "Digital Map of Colonial Frontier Massacres in Australia 1788-1930," <i>Teaching History</i> 54, no. 3 (2020): 13-20.</p> <p>Wegman, Imogen, "Time Layered Cultural Map," <i>Reviews in Digital Humanities</i> 3, no. 11 (2022), https://doi.org/10.21428/3e88f64f.ea03b1ca.</p>
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